

To study awareness of green marketing among consumers, with a special reference Sinnar, Nashik

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Abstract – Green marketing is today hot topic. Companies are used green marketing process, and they are show how our product is beneficial to environment. They are suggesting if you have using or purchasing our product than you are a close friend of environment. for this process companies are using various green marketing tools, techniques and strategies.in this awareness program company are investing huge money. this research are shows that customer is really aware or not aware green marketing .and if they are aware, to see whether they use it in their daily lives or not.in this paper used SPSS software chi square test for research methodology.

Keywords – Green Marketing, Awareness, Environment Friendly, Consumer.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world Degradation of the Environment is a big issue. Every country is facing various problems to save the environment. due to this problem, every country is using various resources, strategies, tools, techniques to save the environment. For this, they appeal to people to use environmentally friendly products so that the environment does not deteriorate and the environment remains safe. From this concept, the term green marketing emerged. green marketing means the product is told in what sense it is environmentally friendly and used various types of promotion tools. Green marketing is a one type of tool to promoting company business.in 1970 first introduce the word green marketing, and then in 1975 the American association arranged the ecological marketing workshop on it.

In the 1980s, awareness of environmental issues, including climate change, grew, which spurred the development of green marketing. Green marketing is part of marketing concept. which does to providing all the awareness of the product. Green marketing it can be said as an awareness program, which is provide all the details of the product and services which is environment friendly.in green marketing following example are say that creating reuseable product, like reusable water bottal.in a packaging example

Encouraging the return and recycling of packaging. in a production example, using sustainable processes in production, reducing waste and reducing emissions. in an Energy example promoting products that use less energy or highlighting the company's use of renewable energy sources.in a corporate social responsibility examples highlighting a company's commitment to environmental initiatives, such as reforestation or carbon offsetting and tree plantation.in a advertisement used Use of eco-friendly materials for advertising and promoting products through sustainable methods. Green loyalty programs involve encouraging customers to choose environmentally friendly products or services through a loyalty program.

II.OBJECTIVE

- 1)To Checking whether consumers are aware of green marketing.
- 2)To Studying through which media, we get information about green marketing products.
- 3)To Study awareness medium and education level.

III. HYPOTHESIS

H1: Above 95% percent people are aware company green marketing program.

H2: There is a correlation between awareness of green marketing and media of green marketing.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

in this study we are using qualitative and quantitative data. in this this primary and secondary data collection methods was used. in the primary data collection, we used Surveys, observations, experiments, questionnaire, personal interview. And secondary data collection we are used various books, Online journals, records, and publications, websites.

Sampling:

To study awareness of green marketing among consumers, in this research paper using random sampling technique to selected 385 representative sample of consumers in Sinnar Tehsil.

V. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Data Analysis:

Analyse the collected data using statistical methods to identify correlations and significant relationships between variables.

ARE YOU AWARE GREEN MARKETING

PIE CHART 1.0

H0: Above 95% percent people are aware company green marketing program.

H1: Above 95% percent people are aware company green marketing program.

In the pie chart 1.0 the 96% percent people agree to they are known the green marketing awareness. Then we accept H1

SOURCES OR MEDIA OF GREEN MARKETING AWARENESS

PIE CHART 2.0

PIE CHART 3.0

H0: There is no correlation between awareness of green marketing and media of green marketing.

H1: There is a correlation between awareness of green marketing and media of green marketing.

Descriptive Statistics
Table 1.0

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
awareness	1.0390	.19375	385
sourcesor media	3.6494	3.10312	385

Correlations Table 2.0

		awareness	Sources or media
awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.413**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	14.416	95.260
	Covariance	.038	.248
	N	385	385
Sources or media	Pearson Correlation	.413**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	95.260	3697.662
	Covariance	.248	9.629
	N	385	385

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2.0 shows the Pearson correlation value is 1, so it's perfectly positive correlation so we accept H1

H1: There is a correlation between awareness of green marketing and media of green marketing.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the 21st century various electronic tools are available for green marketing this is very helpful to industry and service area marketing. Due to this reason 100 percent people are aware green marketing policy, and in that they are changing his purchasing decision. Green marketing is a good promotion policy, to increase awareness of goods and services. Green marketing contributes to the broader understanding of green marketing's role in promoting sustainable consumption.

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

In this research Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study. This research paper is done by primary and secondary sources.

Consent for Publication

I provided informed consent for publication of the Tables, Figure(s), Graphs.

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